

Short communication

New genus and species record of *Sphedanolestes annulatus* Linnavuori (Hemiptera: Reduviidae) for Iran and Jordan

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Abstract. The genus *Sphedanolestes* Stål, 1867, with the species *S. annulatus* Linnavuori, 1961 (Hemiptera: Reduviidae) is recorded for the first time from Iran and Jordan. This species is considered endemic for Israel, and its colour variation is described.

Key words: Heteroptera, Harpactorini, true bugs, new records, faunistics, distribution, Iran, Jordan.

Introduction

The genus *Sphedanolestes* Stål, 1867 (Hemiptera: Reduviidae: Harpactorinae: Harpactorini) comprises 180 species worldwide (Maldonado Capriles 1990) and is distributed in the Palearctic and African regions. In the Palearctic, there are 25 species (Putshkov & Putshkov 1996), the majority of which are known from the Far East, particularly China (Maldonado Capriles 1990).

The genus *Sphedanolestes* wasn't so far confirmed to occur in Central Asia. Two species have been described from this region, *S. lipskii* Kiritchenko, 1914 and *S. oshanini* (Reuter, 1877), but their taxonomic assignment to the genus *Sphedanolestes* is uncertain, and probably they belong to the genus *Rhynocoris* Hahn, 1833 (Putshkov & Putshkov 1996; Putshkov & Moulet 2010).

In the Palearctic Region, *Sphedanolestes* is well known in Europe (Putshkov & Moulet, 2010) where some species have a restricted distribution, such as *S. cingulatus* (Fieber) in Italy, *S. horvathi* Lindberg in Spain and north Africa, *S. riffsensis* Vidal in Morocco, and *S. ornaticollis* Linnavuori in Libya). On the other hand, some species are broadly distributed, such as *S. pulchellus* (Klug) which is found in the Balkans, the near- and mid-East (Putshkov & Moulet 2010; Moulet et al. 2014).

In the Arabic subregion, *Sphedanolestes* is known from Yemen and Oman (Moulet et al. 2014) but so far absent from Iran (Ghahari et al. 2013) and Jordan (Carapezza 2002), although it has been mentioned from Iraq (Moulet 2005).

In this paper, new data on the distribution of *Sphedanolestes annulatus* Linnavuori, 1961, representing the *pulchellus*-group, are given.

Material examined

IRAN: Fars province, 25 Km NW of Shiraz, Sangar Vill., 1♀, 1♂, 23.V.2010, leg. J. Simandl (Fig. 1). **JORDAN:** Ajlun province, 6 km N from Ajlun, 950 m, 1♀, 1♂, 28-30.IV.2018, leg. J. Simandl (Fig. 3); Ajlun province, 2 km W from Sakib, 980 m, 1♂, 19.IV.2018, leg. J. Simandl [all specimens preserved in P. Dioli's collection].

Distribution

Israel [Holotype: Dan, Beit Jubrin, Beit-Sehan, Hago-shrim, Haifa, Jerusalem] (Linnavuori 1961; Putshkov & Putshkov 1996).

Discussion

The *pulchellus*-group was erected by Linnavuori (1969) to group eight little to medium sized species of *Sphedanolestes* (7-9 mm), more or less reddish in color, pale pronotum with black spots. According to Linnavuori (1974) and Moulet et al. (2014) the group is predominantly African and is also known in Arabian subregion.

The general colouration, number and size of pronotal spots and rings on legs are variable, and some taxa were described as new when in fact are only color variants, as in the case of *S. dorchymonti* Dispons, 1968, now a synonym of *S. pulchellus* (Klug, 1830) (Moulet, 2005). Sometimes the species are difficult to recognize, particularly *S. pulchellus* (Klug, 1830) and the African *S. pulcher* Schouteden, 1906 which may be very similar in colour (Linnavuori 1969).

In the Western Palearctic, three species of this group are known, *S. pulchellus* (Klug, 1830), *S. annulatus* Linnavuori, 1961 (Figs 1-3) and *S. aureus* Moulet, 2000.

The male genitalia, in particular the pygophore and phallosome, are characteristic. The pygophore is

slightly conical from back to the front end and the apophysis of posterior edge clearly individualized. In *S. pulchellus* the median process of the pygophore is broad and somewhat convex apically; in *S. annulatus* it is narrow and more or less concave medially (Fig. 4), and in *S. aureus* it is quadrate with acute angles.

Figs 1-2. *Spedanolestes annulatus*. 1. color variation of the specimen from Iran (Shiraz, Sangar). 2. typical coloration of the specimen from Israel (Kyriat Tivon).

Figs 3-4. *Spedanolestes annulatus*. 3. color variation of the specimen from Jordan (Ajlun, Sakib). 4. pygophore, dorsal view, in situ (Jordan, Ajlun).

There are differences between the specimens from Iran and those from Jordan and Israel (Fig. 5), in the colour of the pronotum, scutellum and antenna, but for the rest, the distinctive features of this species are the same than the holotype.

According to Linnavuori (1961, 1969) the head is sometimes yellowish at the apex or entirely black. Antennae are dark brown, the first joint can some-

times be lighter (Fig. 1). Labium is orange. Pronotum is shining, whitish-grey; its anterior lobe and 4 roundish basal spots are black. Pleural region of the thorax is heavily marked with black. Scutellum is black, its apex is yellow. Hemelytra are hyaline, corium with a reddish-brown tinge; veins are reddish-brown, and a membrane is smoke grey. Dorsal abdominal mediotergites are darkened, dorsal laterotergites are orange, with the anterolateral area of each segment black. Ventral surface of the abdomen is orange, sometimes more or less smoke grey medially. Femora are orange; the apex of each femur, two narrow median rings, and a small spot at its base are blackish; tibiae are dark reddish-brown, with the base blackish; tarsi are dark brown. The total body length from 7.0 to 8.0 mm.

The specimens from Iran are lighter in colouration than the holotype described from Israel and have only two spots on the rounded humeral angles of pronotum and only soft grey, almost imperceptible, drawings of the two central spots in the proximal part of pronotum (Fig. 1).

The pattern with well-marked four spots at the base of pronotum (Fig. 2), is the most common in Israel and is distinguished from *S. pulchellus* by having two black rings on the femora and the ventral part of abdomen without markings. In *S. pulchellus*, femora have only one dark median ring and the abdominal venter has large black spots on either side of each segment.

The median process of the pygophore in *S. annulatus*, is narrower and thinner than in *S. pulchellus* as it appears in Linnavuori (1969). The reduction of the two central spots on the pronotum and the absence of spots on the abdomen (which instead are always present in *S. pulchellus*) are distinguishing characters.

The specimens from Jordan, on the other hand, are of the same colouration as those known from Israel (Figs 2 & 3).

Fig. 5. Distributional map of *Spedanolestes annulatus* Linnavuori, 1961.

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